

297 g mol⁻¹ by considering the average repeating unit as structure 1.

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Coumarins from *Eupatorium ayapana*

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EUPATORIUM ayapana Linn. (Compositae), an aromatic undershrub, is a native of America now naturalised in many parts of India. The plant is known for its various medicinal uses¹. Earlier reports described the isolation of ayapin² and

7-methoxycoumarin³ (herniarin) from this plant. The present paper describes the isolation and characterisation of five additional coumarins from this plant.

The combined petroleum ether and chloroform extracts of milled whole plants (1.5 kg) after the usual work up followed by column chromatography and preparative tlc led to the isolation of five compounds of which three designated as compounds A, B and C were new isolates besides ayapin and herniarin. Similarly, the alcoholic extract yielded two compounds designated as compounds D and E.

Compound-A (20 mg) was crystallised from acetone, m.p. 117–18°, C₁₁H₁₀O₄, M⁺ 206; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 720 (α,β -unsaturated lactone) and 1 400–1 600 (Ar); λ_{\max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) 209 (4.58), 255 (3.88) and 316 (4.36); δ (DMSO-d₆) 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.9 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.25 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-3), 7.05 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-5), 7.42 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-6) and 8.05 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-4). The above data were found to be consistent with that reported for daphnetin dimethyl ether⁴.

Compound-B (18 mg) was crystallised from acetone, m.p. 185–86°, C₁₀H₈O₄, M⁺ 192; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 400 (OH), 1 720 (α,β -unsaturated lactone) and 1 400–1 600 (Ar); λ_{\max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) 207 (4.52), 260 (3.99) and 317 (4.15); λ_{\max} (MeOH+KOH) (log ϵ) 279 (4.27) and 327 (4.03) indicative of a phenolic OH group; δ (DMSO-d₆) 3.91 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.28 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-3), 7.1 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-5), 7.3 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-6) and 7.9 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-4). On the basis of the above data compound-B was identified as hydrangetin⁵.

Compound-C (17 mg) was crystallised from acetone, m.p. 169–70°, C₁₀H₈O₄, M⁺ 192; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 400 (OH), 1 720 (α,β -unsaturated lactone) and 1 400–1 600 (Ar); ν_{\max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) 207 (4.84), 257 (3.95) and 322 (4.36); λ_{\max} (MeOH+KOH) (log ϵ) 274 (3.9) and 376 (4.45) indicative of a phenolic OH group; δ (DMSO-d₆) 3.87 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.22 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-3), 6.87 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-5), 7.38 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-6) and 7.93 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, H-4). It was characterised as daphnetin-7-methyl ether⁶.

Compound-D (17 mg) was crystallised from acetone, m.p. 225–26°, C₉H₆O₃, M⁺ 162; ν_{\max} 3 400 (OH) and 1 725 (α,β -unsaturated lactone); λ_{\max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) 204 (4.33) and 324 (4.10); λ_{\max} (MeOH+KOH) (log ϵ) 229 (3.94) and 370 (4.25) indicative of phenolic OH moiety; δ (CD₂COCD₂) 6.1 (1H, d, J 10 Hz, H-3), 7.74 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-4) and 6.8–7.4 (3H, m, ArH). It was identified as umbelliferone⁶.

Compound-E (22 mg) was crystallised from acetone, m.p. 255–56°, C₉H₆O₄, M⁺ 190; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 400 (OH) and 1 725 (α,β -unsaturated lactone); λ_{\max} (MeOH) (log ϵ) 209 (4.51), 262 (3.88) and 327 (4.10); λ_{\max} (MeOH+KOH) (log ϵ) 211 (4.51), 279 (4.06) and 379 (4.03) indicative of phenolic OH group; λ_{\max} (MeOH+AlCl₃) (log ϵ)

211 (4.5), 276 (4.10) and 347 (4.2); λ_{\max} (MeOH + AlCl₃ + HCl) (log ϵ) 211 (3.92), 278 (3.88) and 329 (4.05) indicative of 2 adjacent OH groups; δ (DMSO-d₆) 6.19 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, H-3), 6.7 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, H-5), 6.8 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, H-6), 7.9 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, H-4), 9.27 (1H, br s, D₂O exchangeable), 9.8 (1H, br s, D₂O exchangeable). The above data were in agreement with those reported for daphnetin⁵. There appears to be no report on the occurrence of daphnetin dimethyl ether, hydrangetin, daphnetin-7-methyl ether and daphnetin in *Eupatorium* species.

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Flavonol Glycosides from the Leaves of *Sterculia urens* Roxb.

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EARLIER work on *Sterculia* revealed the presence of 6-oxygenated flavone derivatives¹⁻³, but recent work on *S. urens*⁴ showed only a C-methyl chalcone which tempted us to reinvestigate this work. We report here the isolation and characterisation of two flavonol diglycosides, quercetin-3-O-(6''-O- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl)- β -D-glucoside and kaempferol-3-O-(6''-O- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl)- β -D-glucoside along with four non-flavonoidic compounds. The presence of flavonol rhamnoglucoside is the first example in *Sterculia* genus (Sterculiaceae). The occurrence of flavonol diglycosides in the plant may serve as a useful taxonomic marker.

The dark gummy concentrate of the methanol extract of air-dried leaves (collected from Botanical Garden, Qila, Aligarh) was fractionated into petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°), benzene and water.

The greenish mass obtained from petrol and benzene extracts upon chromatography (Si-gel) and elution with petrol–benzene (9 : 1, 1 : 1) and benzene–EtOAc (9 : 1, 1 : 1) yielded four compounds which were identified as 3-acetyl- β -amyirin, β -amyirin, β -sitosterol and ester of terephthalic acid by spectral studies and comparison with authentic samples.

The brown mass (3 g) obtained from the water extract upon column chromatography (Si-gel) and elution with chloroform–methanol (4 : 1) and preparative pc (Whatman no. 3, n-BuOH–HOAc–H₂O, 4 : 1 : 5) yielded two flavonoids, compounds A (*R_f* 0.45, 300 mg) and B (*R_f* 0.54, 200 mg).

Compound-A ; R=OH
Compound-B ; R=H

Compound A : Compound A, as yellow needle shaped crystals (MeOH), m.p. 188–89°, on hydrolysis with 8% HCl afforded quercetin (m.p., m.m.p., co-tlc and uv spectra) and two sugars, D-glucose (*R_f* 0.18) and L-rhamnose (*R_f* 0.36) (pc, Whatman no. 1, n-BuOH–HOAc–H₂O, 6 : 1 : 2; *R_f*, co-pc and colour developed with aniline hydrogen phthalate found identical with authentic sugars). On partial hydrolysis with 1% H₂SO₄ for 1 h, it yielded only L-rhamnose as the sugar (pc) and a yellow compound, m.p. 235–37° showing the rhamnose as terminal sugar. The yellow compound on further hydrolysis (enzymic, emulsin from almond at 35–40° for 70 h or acidic 8% HCl) gave quercetin and D-glucose. The release of D-glucose by emulsin hydrolysis suggested its β -configuration in the linkage. Permethylolation of compound A followed by hydrolysis (HOAc–HCl–H₂O, 7 : 3 : 10) yielded quercetin 5,7,3',4'-tetramethyl ether, m.p. 194°, 2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-L-rhamnose (*R_f* 0.75) identified by chromatographic method⁵. The release of these partially methylated sugars suggested the pyranose conformations of the two sugar moieties. The partially methylated aglycone showed characteristic bathochromic shift of 60 nm in band-I with AlCl₃ confirming C-3 glycosylation⁶ in compound A. ¹H nmr spectrum (CDCl₃) of compound A–acetate, m.p. 136°, showed signals at δ 2.30–2.45 due to four phenolic and at δ 1.92–2.15 for six alcoholic acetoxy groups, suggesting it to be a diglycoside. A multiplet centered at δ 0.91 and a doublet at δ 4.52 (*J* 2 Hz) were ascribed to rhamnose